

IMPACT OF THE MINING INDUSTRY ON PEOPLE AND THE ENVIRONMENT

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ANNOSTATSIYA. The article considers the impact of the mining industry on people and the environment, pollution of nature, pollution of the environment, negative consequences of using natural resources. Rational use of minerals, processes of their extraction and processing, methods of uranium extraction are important. Since the beginning of mankind, all natural resources of the earth's crust have been happily used for their needs. For this purpose, more than a million tons of natural land landscapes have been developed.

Enter. The negative impact of humans on nature intensified especially during the scientific and technological revolution. With the establishment of various enterprises and factories, mining enterprises of mineral resources are releasing 3.8 billion tons of ash and dust into the atmosphere as waste. This dust contains 1.9 billion arsenic, 1.2 billion tons of toxic zinc, 68 million tons of zinc, 4 million tons of lead, 20-22 thousand tons of cadmium, 50 thousand tons of nickel, 4 thousand tons of fluorine, phosphorus (R₂O₃) 35 million tons, smob 15-48 thousand tons of pesticides, 3.2 million tons of some toxic substances are spreading into the environment. This, in turn, has a negative impact on our ecology and human health. Every year, 130 billion tons of ore are mined on the scale of our planet. Currently, 9-12% of the developed land is for agriculture, 22-25% for pastures, 2-3% for roads, and 1% for mineral resources. is correct. This means that 17-24 tons of waste products come out of each square kilometer. To date, humanity may be wiped out from the face of the earth for 3 different reasons; 1) due to nuclear 2) ecological 3) spiritual disasters. Traditional methods of extracting and beneficiating minerals are distinguished by the release of a large amount of waste. Waste dumped in large areas, as well as concentrated factories and wastewater, cause disruption and negative consequences in all components of the biosphere. As a result of constant air and water pollution, plants and unique species of animals will disappear. As a result of the analysis of a number of sources, it became clear that the sharp destruction of ecology, the appropriation of natural regions has a negative effect on human health year after year. One of such expensive ores is uranium, which in the process of extraction, processing and storage has a negative impact on the

workers of enterprises (miners, equipment operators, etc.) and on the surrounding residential areas and environment. By reducing the dose for miners, ventilation increases the radiation load on the residents of the surrounding villages. It is very important that this load continues even after the closure of the mines. The closed uranium mine in Bulgaria is located on the outskirts of the village of Yelinet, so there is a lot of radon in the residential buildings. Among the 2600 inhabitants of the village, lung cancer cases are 30% per year. This is the result of the location of the mine close to the population. In gold mining, technologies for separating precious metals from mineral mixtures are used, which is accompanied by the release of toxic components into the atmosphere. Toxic water is released from the waste, which poisons groundwater and wastewater. The chemical composition of the soil changes. leads to the mutation of plants. As a result of the pollution of agricultural lands, the productivity decreases sharply, as a result, food shortages occur. Another chemical that pollutes the environment is toxic chemicals and chemical fertilizers. We call poisonous chemical preparations pesticides (Latin water pestis- poison and cid- to kill). We divide them into three groups according to their chemical composition: 1. inorganic compounds (marginium, copper, zinc, fluorine, barium, mercury, sulfur compounds, chlorates and other compounds); 2. chemical substances obtained from plants, fungi, bacteria (pyrethroids, anabazin, nicotine, bacterial preparations, antibiotics, etc.); 3. organic compounds, they are active substances in terms of effect. Traditional methods of obtaining mineral raw materials and their enrichment are characterized by a large amount of waste. Waste dumped on large areas, as well as concentrated factories and waste water, cause disruption and negative consequences in all components of the biosphere - air and water bodies are polluted, as a result of which land resources are degraded, many species of plants and fauna disappear. During the analysis of a number of sources, the main environmental problems and the aspects that affect the natural environment and people as part of it were identified.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The activity of the uranium mining industry affects, first of all, the workers of enterprises (miners, equipment operators, etc.), and secondly, the surrounding settlements and natural inhabitants. It includes: contamination of mine waters with uranium and other radionuclides; dumping waste water into groundwater; washing of radionuclides from contaminated areas with rain and their spread into the environment; extraction of radon from mines, waste rock waste and waste; washing of radionuclides from waste, then pouring into

natural waters; erosion of waste systems with the dispersal of toxic substances by wind and water; contamination of groundwater and surface water with toxic non-radioactive substances, such as heavy metals and reagents used in ore processing. A tracer of uranium contamination can be the isotopic ratio of $^{234}\text{U} / ^{238}\text{U}$, which is close to the equilibrium value in ores and mineral tailings, and significantly exceeds its value in surface groundwater. The main air pollutants in the traditional methods of uranium ore mining and processing: dust generated during mining, transportation, crushing of ores, storage in landfills and long-term storage of waste from the hydrometallurgical industry, including dust containing radioactive substances. . Radioactive substances in mine dust include long-term emitters (U, Ra, Po, Io, RaD, Th) that can have a harmful effect on living organisms by inhaling contaminated mine air near ventilation devices and production air outlets. gases (CO_2 , CO, H_2S , nitrogen oxides, NH_3 , H_2SO_4 vapors, etc.) released as a result of chemical interaction of reagents with ores and intermediate products during blasting and during hydrometallurgical processing. Despite the well-organized dust removal in underground mining (the amount of dust in the mine atmosphere does not exceed $1 \text{ mg} / \text{m}^3$), in the transportation, transportation and crushing of ores, as well as unbalanced ores, waste rock and waste, only one medium productivity and hydrometallurgical plant along with tens of tons of dust per year. A particularly significant amount of dust enters the atmosphere during open pit mining, due to the large volume of loads and the difficulty of suppressing dust in winter. Large amounts of groundwater are constantly withdrawn from uranium mines to prevent them from drying out during mining. This water flows into rivers, streams and lakes. Regarding the protection of surface and especially underground water during the extraction of uranium by underground leaching, the opinion of experts is unclear. Differences in the calculations are caused by the formation of tens and hundreds of thousands of sulfuric acids or other solvents in the underground water during several years of underground leaching of the ore horizons. concentration of dissolved reactant. When dissolving pollution in a general sense, the introduction of this amount of solvent naturally gives reason to talk about groundwater pollution. As a result of physico-chemical processes of underground solutions in technological solutions (production and working), some components are allowed for drinking water and water used for economic purposes. Uranium mining wastes also pose an environmental hazard when ore bodies are opened, in the construction of underground mines, in the laying of drifts through non-metallic zones, and unnecessary rock is extracted from open

mines. Residues of rocks raised to the surface of the Earth usually contain more radionuclides than the surrounding rocks. All of these wastes pose a threat to local residents because they continue to produce radon even after the mines are closed. Due to the low content of uranium in the ores, processing at hydrometallurgical plants takes up large areas, including sanitary zones, and the volume of landfills is equal in terms of the amount of mined and processed commercial ores. Residual waste not only renders large areas of land completely unfit for agricultural use. Since the development time of mining enterprises from exploration to production is about 20 years, in the near future, uranium mining companies should focus on ensuring the future development of the uranium mining industry. In particular: the fullness and completeness of the exploitation of underground resources, which implies the complete elimination of raw material losses and the minimization of the amount of waste by processing it into secondary resources, as well as the extraction of valuable components that accompany them 'to provide. This increases production profitability and attracts additional funds for the organization of environmental protection measures in order to reduce the impact of anthropogenic pressure on the environment. In modern technologies of extraction of mineral raw materials, the main destructive processes associated with drilling, blasting, splitting, crushing, transportation of rock mass, its processing, enrichment prevail. These processes are accompanied by rock pressure, rock movement, rock shocks, gas outbursts, dust, endogenous and exogenous fires, etc. Often, some of them have a large size, gas and dust explosions in coal mines are especially dangerous for workers. Water treatment and wastewater treatment are becoming increasingly important in the global mining industry. Water scarcity and increasing environmental pollution have significantly changed the attitude to the proper use of water resources in mining enterprises. To be able to reuse it (as technological water or to cover water shortages in arid regions), improve the water consumption coefficient and become less dependent on external water supply limitations. 1 Wise use of water. Water use efficiency and standards Mining companies use large amounts of water. Often, a single gold mine uses hundreds of cubic meters of water per hour for process operations. Wastewater of this volume can pose a serious threat to the environment and the population. No wonder mining companies around the world spend more than \$7 billion a year on water. To a large extent, this is due to the strengthening of standards for the rational use of water resources in the field and, at the same time, increased control over their implementation. The new standards set maximum daily loads

for each component of waste. Special attention is paid to the protection of human health, aquatic flora and fauna. Water from external sources used as drinking water in the organization, including in remote places of work, must be purified from mechanical impurities and microorganisms to the level in accordance with current standards.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Water for production processes can be obtained by reusing waste water. Alternative sources can also be used to obtain process water, such as pre-treated municipal wastewater, treated surface water or groundwater. Thus, water from these sources can be used as make-up water in ore processing or mineral processing technology, boilers or cooling towers. It is necessary to assess and analyze the level of impact of mining enterprises (water resources) on the environment. Unfortunately, at the current stage of social development, the mining industry has the greatest impact on human activity and the natural environment. From the point of view of the environment, mining enterprises are important sources of damage and pollution of all elements of the biosphere. Therefore, it is very important and necessary to assess and forecast the level of their impact on the environment, as they allow to develop effective environmental protection measures in advance to avoid irreparable damage to the environment. Since humanity today extracts and processes minerals on a large scale, the task of mountain ecology is to minimize the impact of their life processes on the environment, which is important for ensuring the safety of life. The fact is that in the process of extracting minerals, almost all components of the ecosystem are negatively affected: terrain, atmosphere, surface and underground water, soil and plant cover and fauna.

Summary: In the future. Organizational, economic, technical and other measures to ensure compliance with the quality standards of mining enterprises, whose activities are closely related to the impact on the environment, environmental components (atmospheric air, surface and underground water) it is necessary to implement the measures) it is appropriate for them to conduct work in accordance with ecological and sanitary-hygienic standards and regulations. Because we really want our future generations to enjoy this beautiful and unrepeatable nature of ours, to grow up healthy and strong. It is necessary to take a lot of measures so that the successors of our generations deserve such happiness or, on the contrary, do not face the problems of shortage of clean air, drinking water and ecologically suitable food! Our children deserve to bathe in clear streams and pick flowers in endless green

valleys. There is a proverb about us: "What you sow is what you reap!" So, whatever we do to ourselves, let's not leave our future generations without such happiness!

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